

**PEACE-BUILDING AND NATION-BUILDING AS ELIXIR
FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: THE MOSES
EXAMPLE HEBREWS 11:24-27**

BY

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Abstract

Peace-building and nation-building are twin concepts that are integral to sustainable development anywhere in the world. Scholars have treated these concepts on national and international levels dwelling on topics like United Nations peace missions, bilateral talks and the signing of memoranda for peace and development by the global communities primarily on the Middle East, Russia-Ukraine, North Korea-South Korea; in Nigeria, the academia, political analysts and commentators have also followed suit with little or no attention paid to the importance of the application of these concepts within nations, especially Nigeria to discovering why sustainable development has eluded the country despite all the peace-building and nation-building efforts. This paper, therefore, examines the factors responsible for the deprivation of sustainable development in Nigeria using Moses (Hebrews 11:24-27) as an example. Offline and online data are collected using the literature research method and are analyzed descriptively and theologically. For Moses, choosing to leave his high estate to be mistreated along with the commoners was a necessary sacrifice for nation-building. Nigerian politicians and those in authority can emulate this example for sustainable development to be achieved.

Keywords: Peace-building, Nation-building, Sustainable development, Moses, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Peace-building and nation-building are central to premium leadership that can lead to sustainable development. These concepts can only be achieved when leaders, political or religious, identify with the suffering of their people with

empathy and compassion, and have the will to solve the people's problems through justice and equity. It is conceded that the bulk does not stop at every leader's table, but it is also true that peace and nation-building can be achieved only when all hands are on deck.

The problem with leadership in Nigeria is that many, if not all, leaders feel that they are doing the citizens a favour. In addition, because Nigeria has no social contract, given that the country's foundation was laid on the greed of the imperialists in 1914. Those who have found themselves in power often feel that it is their time to make the most of the opportunities that come their way. By operating a feeding bottle federalism, leadership in the country is viewed from the wrong side of the telescope, namely religion and ethnicity. Many scholars have addressed these problems, but one aspect is consistently overlooked in their scholarship. This is why Nigerian leaders are not able to leave or resign from their posts to identify with their people like Moses did.

It is very uncommon in this part of the world to see a leader resign in protest to draw attention to or highlight the suffering of their people. They remain in power far away and high above their constituents, enjoying themselves while coming home only occasionally to showcase their opulence. This paper aims to investigate this anomaly, malaise, and malady to deepen the discussion and open new vistas for leadership to attain sustainable development through peace and nation building. This is not intended to be a conclusive paper but a herald for such conversation and a call to leaders that leadership is not about perpetuating oneself in power for decades, but the impact. Leaders who do not have empathy and compassion for the plight of their people are just occupying space, and their irrelevance and greed will be their undoing someday.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

The key working terms for this paper are clarified in the ensuing paragraphs:

Peace-building

Adegbami in his explanation of the term 'peace-building' explained that "the term was added into the political lexicon of governance and states' administration in 1975 when Johan Galtung coined the term in his pioneering work titled "Three Approaches to Peace: Peacekeeping, Peacemaking, and Peace-building."¹ To illumine the concept, he argued that the word is made up of dependent and independent variables namely 'peace' and 'building.' For him, therefore, "peace is indispensable to peace-building, such that without peace, there can be no peace-building. In other words, peace is key or the heart of peace-building; it is only when there is peace that one can build on it."²

This paper understands the concept differently. It reasons that peace-building is an attempt at laying the foundation for the establishment or entrenchment of peace in

the society, especially in a milieu of crisis or insecurity, as is the case with contemporary Nigeria. It is with this understanding that the narrative of this paper is crafted. There is no doubt that this is the understanding he himself had in mind when he wrote these words: “peace-building is building an environment for negotiation, reconciliation, mutual understanding, and compromise that allows for resolving conflict issues before it degenerates into violence and conflict.”³

“Peace-building is the identification and support of measures needed for transformation toward a more sustainable, peaceful relationship and structures of governance, to avoid a relapse into conflict.” It is also perceived as an attempt to conquer the structural, relational, and cultural contradictions hastily causing conflict, especially in strong support of peacemaking and peacekeeping. Inspirations of peace-building are drawn from developmental imperatives facing humanity and conflict resolution initiatives.”⁴

Nation-building

Peace-building is a precursor to nation-building. This assertion is premised on the fact that no nation can thrive in an era of chaos, anarchy, and insecurity, the result of which is a total lack of peace. This is the case with Nigeria. The country has been beset by protracted insecurity that has seemingly defied all efforts at resolving the phenomenon.

According to Eme and Onyishi, “Nation-building is the intervention in the affairs of a nation-state for the purpose of changing the state’s method of government. Nation-building also includes efforts to promote institutions which will provide for economic well-being and social equity.”⁵

The concept of nation-building implies the creation of nation-states from disparate socio-economic, religious, ethnic, and geographical elements. This, according to him, entails the translation of diffuse and unorganized sentiments of nationalism into the spirit of citizenship through the creation of state institutions that can translate into policy and programs in line with the aspirations of the citizenry. Nations do not happen by mere historical accident; instead, they are built by men and women with vision and resolve.” Similarly, “Ntui (2019) opined that Nation-building is the product of conscious statecraft, not happenstance. Nation-building is always a work-in-progress, a dynamic process in constant need of nurturing.” This means nation-building entails “conscious efforts to weld together a plural society to enhance development without necessarily jeopardizing ethnic identity (Ojo, 2009). This is why Ake (1979) asserted that “nation-building is synonymous with national integration. To him, National integration is the process of bringing together culturally and socially discrete groups into a single territorial unit and establishing a national identity.”⁶

Nation-building has essential aspects. According to Ntui (2019), these critical aspects include, first, building a political entity that corresponds to a given territory based on generally accepted rules, norms, principles, and common citizenship. Second, it is also about building institutions that symbolize the political entity. These institutions include bureaucracy, the economy, the judiciary, universities, civil service, and civil organizations. Nation-building is about creating a shared sense of purpose, a collective sense of destiny, and a unified vision of belonging. It is, therefore, about building the tangible and intangible threads that hold a political entity together and give it a sense of purpose.⁷

Sustainable Development

In reference to a publication in 1987, Vitalis submitted that sustainable development is development that “meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”⁸ Barbier also defined sustainable development as “one which is directly concerned with increasing the natural standard of living of the poor at the grassroots level which could be quantitatively measured in terms of increased food, real income, educational services, health care, sanitation, water supply and the like.” For Pearce, it is “a vector of desirable social objectives such that an increase in real income per capita, an improvement in health and nutrition, educational achievement, access to resources, a fairer distribution of income and increase in basic freedom.” Winpenny opined that sustainable development is “that which leaves our total patrimony, including natural environmental assets, intact over a particular period.” Tietenberg posited that it is “the willingness and the ability of the present generation to devise a means of using depletive resources such that future generations, at a minimum, would be left no worse off than current generation.” In the same vein, “development is sustainable if, in the process of attaining it, the needs of the future generations are not compromised” (WCED 1987).⁹ Sustainable development aims at the creation of sustainable improvements in the quality of life for all people as the principal goal of development policy. Besides increasing economic growth and meeting basic needs, the aim of improving living standards includes several more specific goals, such as enhancing people’s health and education opportunities, providing everyone with the chance to participate in public life, helping to ensure a clean environment, and promoting intergenerational equality. Sustainable development also aims to maximize the net benefits of economic development, while maintaining the stock of all environmental and natural resource assets (physical, human, and natural) over time.¹⁰

THE NIGERIAN CONTEXT

From this juncture, the paper contextualizes the concepts clarified above to the state of things as are obtainable in Nigeria. To begin, Nigeria is sixty-three years since gaining political independence. In recent years, it can be said that the peace that could have ushered in nation-building and sustainable development has been elusive. The blame for this can be plausibly attributed to the political elite, who are always part of every succeeding administration in the country. Their presence in governments over the years is merely showmanship rather than craft, as there is nothing to account for peace-building, nation-building, and sustainable development. The fault lines are traceable to 1914, yet this is not an excuse for the country's predicament.

In their study, Ibrahim and Nurudeen asserted, in the literature review, that Social Contract Theory is the basis for the founding of the state. However, the postulation of Felix & Obina (2020), as cited in their work, that "the unification of Nigeria in 1914 was not done in consultation with the people; hence we cannot talk of the Social Contract as the basis for the founding of Nigeria. Rather, Nigeria was a creation of British overlords who were primarily interested in the colony for its economic benefits and administrative convenience. They created the entity without consideration for their diverse ethnic, cultural, and historical background. It was therefore not with the consent of the people"¹¹ aligns with the thesis of this paper.

They also cited Muyiwa & Anthony (2016), who shared the same sentiments with Felix and Obinna when they argued that the "colonial authorities that created Nigeria consciously prepared the new state for perpetual conflict and instability. This, they argued, was to satisfy their craving for the control of the people's mind and resources." They further argued that "social contract theories are a demonstration of the rational capacity of the people to develop a political destiny that will guarantee freedom to the people. They also assist in building institutions that ensure man's collective efforts towards achieving good ends. Unfortunately, at governance process in the post-colonial era reveals that the Nigerian ruling elite use ethnic and religious cleavages to feather their selfish interests."¹² In a similar deposition, Keneneth & Joseph (2019) averred that "the Nigerian state, in collaboration with its actors in power, have failed to adhere to the tenets of Social Contract theory as espoused by its proponents. This non-adherence is responsible for the failure of the efforts to build a nation in Nigeria."¹³

Amadi and Eweka, in similar thinking, opined that a heterogeneous country like Nigeria needs a well-articulated leadership structure that could foster the spirit of "live and let live." The contrary is the case as they further posited that leadership is the bane of sustainable development in Nigeria.¹⁴ Similarly, Gbandi and Amisah argued that the essence of leadership is the people, i.e., the followership.

The implication is that a lack of focused leadership is a problem that can lead to a lack of sustainable development. For them, that is the major problem of insecurity and lack of growth in Nigeria.¹⁵ Anekwe also lamented the poverty of quality and positive leadership that has beset the country, concluding that “Leadership and good governance are crucial to realizing any giant stride taken in pursuit of development anywhere in the world; Nigeria is not an exception.”¹⁶

THE MOSES EXAMPLE: HEBREWS 11:24-27

By faith, Moses, when he had grown up, refused to be known as the son of Pharaoh’s daughter. He chose to be mistreated along with the people of God rather than to enjoy the pleasures of sin for a short time. He regarded disgrace for the sake of Christ as of greater value than the treasures of Egypt, because he was looking ahead to his reward. By faith he left Egypt, not fearing the king’s anger; he persevered because he saw him who is invisible (Heb. 11:24-27 NIV).

In this short periscope, there are things that Moses did that are worthy of emulation by the political elite in Nigeria. There can be no doubt that Moses was a nation-builder. To be a nation-builder, one must align with the goals of their people and seek the interests of the people for the common good, pursuing such goals and ideals with a sincerity of purpose. One thing that must be made clear here is that Moses was an elite, well-brought-up young man who could have become a Pharaoh in Egypt. He was living in utmost luxury in the palace (akin to presidential palace or government house – Aso Rock in Nigeria). At the same time, his people were everyday enslaved people laboring in slave camps far away from him. He was free not to even identify with them and let them suffer while he focused on his personal ambition of becoming a Pharaoh in the future – *emi lokan*.¹⁷

Yet, Moses had faith in the identity of his people and chose to identify with them, to be mistreated and disgraced rather than settle for the pleasures his palatial habitat and the treasures his status afforded him. When he was fully grown, he reckoned that he could not be a child of an alien and enjoy while his people suffer. As a nation-builder, he reasoned that it is far more rewarding to have the interests of the people at heart and damn the consequences; hence, he persevered. He resigned from his high position. He was going to leave behind him luxurious armored SUV rides, presidential jet for owambe trips accompanied by a phalanx of security retinue armed to the teeth with koboko to flog any commoner that approaches to uncomfortable proximity, free money and other freebies at the expense of the long-suffering people.

A CASE FOR NIGERIAN LEADERS

It is a truism that states created through a social contract will have well-established leaders who will follow the terms of that contract with a sincerity of purpose. Such leaders are peace-builders and nation-builders who have the interest of their nation at heart. Unfortunately, Nigeria is a child of circumstances. It was conceived in greed and born as a dairy cow. Those who created the Nigerian state did not have the interest of the people they were forcing to stay together at heart. It was all about the interest of imperial greed. The local politicians who took power in 1960 also viewed Nigeria through the greedy eyes of the imperialists. Their greed and parochialism took local coloration, as rather than become peace-builders and nation-builders, they chose to be ethnic jingoists and religious bigots.

Nigerian leaders have always masked the pursuit of their personal ambition using ethnic and religious sentiments to assume power and become more vicious in their bid to secure such offices. They remain in power as long as they are alive at the expense of the same ethnic group they used to secure the office. In death, their children succeed them. The route to governance is deliberately made so costly that it is left for them and their children to bear. Those who could have made a difference are so impoverished that they are unable to afford a hundred million naira or fifty million naira for a form to contest for the presidency or governorship primaries, respectively. There is also a need for plenty of money to rent thugs, buy over electoral officials, and hire some religious leaders. This is what is called “structure” in Nigeria’s electoral lexicon.

Thus, aspiring leaders swear allegiance to these political oligarchs and godfathers and vigorously defend their interests. Without ideals or ideologies, there is no way one can hold these leaders accountable, hence they pitch their tent in any political party or with any political leader they feel their interests could be achieved. As long as they remain in power, they do not care about what happens to their people. Few examples will suffice.

Mr. George Akume was the governor of Benue State from 1999 to 2007, serving on the platform of the People’s Democratic Party (PDP). He became a senator in the PDP but later decamped to the All Progressives Congress (APC) when his interests were threatened. He later became a minister in the administration of Muhammadu Buhari for eight years. Even though he is a Christian, he ardently campaigned for the same faith ticket of Mr. Tinubu and Shettima, and he has been rewarded. He is now the Secretary to the Government of the Federation. While in Buhari’s administration as minister and now as SGF, his people back home were systematically targeted by the Fulani herdsmen militia, who disturbed the peace of villages, killed locals in cold blood with wanton recklessness, raped women, and took over their ancestral farmlands, he remains unperturbed because he is keeping

table manners: “you don’t talk while eating.” He never protested the killings of his people, the injustice, and the sufferings meted out to his people by the same administration he was the senate chairman, in the Army, and later a minister.

Instead, he accused his state government of being the killers of the people, exonerating the Fulani herders just to scurry favours from Buhari by assuring him that the party would mobilise support in Benue State for Buhari’s reelection in 2019. This was in total disregard of reports that herder attacks consumed hundreds of lives. He snitched:

We know those who were behind that; the government was behind that. I am talking about the state government, through the livestock guards. They knew what was going on. So it is now a thing of the past. “Everything that is going on there is fraudulent in Benue State, and the people are simply tired of this misinformation that they have been receiving. The narrative has changed; it is not a question of herders, we are not talking about religious and ethnic bigotry, we are talking about the performance of the government.”¹⁸

Samuel Ortom, the then governor of the state, described the comments from Akume as “shocking and unfortunate; Akume appears ready to sacrifice his people.”¹⁹ Moses identified with his people and chose to be mistreated along with them. He saw his suffering with them as nation-building. Moses built the nation of Israel. Akume’s Tiv nation is subsumed under the Hausa-Fulani hegemony, but that does not seem to bother him as long as his nest is feathered. To identify with his people will mean losing a meal ticket.

Simon Lalong, just like Akume, was a Speaker of the Plateau State House of Assembly. He found his way to become the governor of the state, where he served for eight years (2015–2023). Though a Christian, he was the campaign chairman for the Muslim-Muslim ticket of Tinubu and Shettima. While an APC governor, he was more aligned with the propensities of the Caliphate. His people were massacred while he served as the governor. Till now, while he is a minister in this government, Plateau State indigenes are still being killed. It does not look like he is aware. Identifying with his people and leaving the government in protest will mean losing a meal ticket.

There are kidnappers in the forests of the South-West. They are kidnapping the locals for ransom, then raping them and hacking them to death even after hefty ransoms are paid. Farmers are killed on their farmlands and their crops are fed to cows. The security agencies arrest the farmers who react in defense of their farms, leaving the aggressors. For example, in Ondo state, Olu Falae’s farm has been under intense and sustained attacks. These invasions have received extensive coverage from news outlets, yet have not prompted commensurate action from the government.²⁰ If this is happening to a person of Olu Falae’s status in society, one

can only imagine what the masses are going through. There is no known record of any local politician identifying with these people or resigning from the government in protest as a nation-builder.

The same applies to some of our church leaders. While the Muslims stand up in defence of their own ranks, some Christian leaders with eagle eyes are always on the prowl for opportunities for meal tickets. They disregard the persecution and massacre of Christian communities as it is happening in Benue, Plateau, Nassarawa, Taraba, Adamawa, Borno, and Kaduna, among other states. Instead, they churn out prophecies in favour of such persecutor governments and ask the church to pray for those in government because they are God sent. The axiom that “when you take a fat cock to the native doctor, all incantations will be in your favour” is thus proven to be true.

The Federal Government of Nigeria has approved the purchase of Sport Utility Vehicles (SUVs) for the National Assembly members. Each unit of the luxurious SUV will cost one hundred and sixty million naira for each senator and almost the same sum for each member of the House of Representatives. This is coming in these difficult economic times that are distressing the citizens.²¹ Till now, it isn't easy to see any lawmaker who is desirous of standing with the masses, as all of them are itching for the vehicles. It will cost ₦57.6 billion.²² To build a resilient nation that will foster sustainable development, political and religious leaders must align with the plight of the masses and stand in solidarity with them. The contrary is the case in Nigeria because everyone is for themselves.

Julius Abure, the National Chairman of the Labour Party, advised the lawmakers of their party not to accept this kind of frivolous largesse and insensitive expenditure at this time of suffering. Still, their responses showed they will not heed the advice:

It is saddening that, with deepening poverty among Nigerians, the administration has decided to increase its appetite for a life of opulence to mock hardworking but underprivileged Nigerians. How else can any government justify the bloated Federal Executive Council of 48 cabinet ministers, with each of them given three luxury four-wheel drive vehicles on the first day in office, paid for and fueled by taxpayers? This is notwithstanding hundreds of presidential and ministerial aides, as well as numerous aides to the aides who the government is funding. These vehicles will cost Nigerians approximately ₦57.6 billion, which is happening at a time when the government claims it cannot afford to increase the minimum wage of ₦30,000 monthly for workers. As things stand today, inflation is likely to hit 30 per cent by December 2023, yet

all they are concerned about is the comfort of a privileged few who found themselves in public office.²³

Below are some of the responses of the Labour Party legislators:²⁴ Ngozi Okolie, representing Delta Aniocha North and South, said,

The SUVs are meant to aid our jobs as lawmakers, particularly as they relate to our oversight functions. Yes, he can say that the economy is struggling, but having one official vehicle as federal lawmakers isn't frivolous; it's a necessity.

Stainless Chijioke Nwodo, lawmaker representing Igbo Etiti and Uzo-Uwani constituencies in Enugu State, is the most banal of all:

National Assembly members should pray for the President and give him three 'Gbosas' for his magnanimity to the lawmakers. Nobody in the National Assembly is against the SUV. When the SUV comes, we will collect it and use it to bring more benefits to our constituencies, because in the real sense, it is for the constituents.

The banality in their comments is baffling, but then that underlines the thinking of average Nigerian leaders who think they are doing the poor citizens a favour. They need to ride luxury SUVs to visit their constituents who are neck-deep in multi-dimensional poverty for oversight duties. They do not even pretend to share in the plight of their constituents.

CONCLUSION

The only reason Moses left behind the pleasures of his palatial abode, the treasures of Egypt, and the possibility of becoming a Pharaoh was that he had the interest of his people at heart. He felt that to be able to build that nation, he would have to identify with his people, not betray them. The only reason Nigerian politicians cannot stand with their people and suffer with them is because of the pleasures and treasures they get from the perks of office or the possibility of a future office. For them, personal ambition is paramount and preferred over peace-building and nation-building. That is why it is difficult to hear of any Nigerian official resigning from an office in a government under which their people are suffering in poverty and squalor as it is this time. They value their personal progress at the expense of national growth and sustainable development. The Nigerian leaders have a lot to learn from the Moses example if they are out for nation-building and sustainable development.

Let people with low incomes breathe!

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